

1 **Paleoecological insights from coprolites and their inclusions from the Permian Rio**
2 **do Rasto Formation, Brazil**

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20
21 **Abstract**

22
23 Coprolites have provided valuable insights into paleoecological relationships, such as
24 predation and parasitism, as well as taphonomic and paleoenvironmental conditions.
25 However, few studies have focused on coprolites from the Rio do Rasto Formation,
26 despite their abundance in this formation. Here, we analyze and describe 97 coprolites
27 from 11 sites within the Rio do Rasto Formation (middle/upper Permian) of Paraná
28 Basin (southern Brazil). External and internal features were examined, classifying the
29 material into four morphotypes: heteropolar (12%), amphipolar (11%), indeterminate
30 spiral (40%) and non-spiral (37%). Alimentary inclusions, such as fish scales, teeth,
31 bone fragments, plants and insect wing, were identified in nearly all specimens.
32 Additionally, microorganisms and parasites were preserved within the fecal matrix,
33 including bacilli bacteria, Actinomycete biofilm, fungal hyphae and spores, Nostocales
34 and Chroococcales cyanobacteria, and cestode eggs. The bacteria and fungi originated

35 from the intestinal tract of the producer before the extrusion, while the cyanobacteria
36 were ingested from the water where these animals lived in. The new occurrence of
37 cestode eggs provide direct evidence of parasitism and corroborates the existence of this
38 relationship from at least the Permian. The phosphatic composition of the coprolites,
39 combined with bacterial and fungal activity, was crucial for preserving delicate organic
40 remains (e.g., plant and insect wing) and organisms (e.g., parasites). These findings
41 enhance our understanding of the producer diet, paleoecological interactions, and the
42 microenvironment within the feces.

43

44 *Key words:* Paraná Basin; paleoecological relationships; paleoparasitology

45 **1. Introduction**

46 Coprolites (fossilized feces) are trace fossils that provide valuable insights into
47 intestinal tract morphology, diet, feeding behavior, taphonomy and paleoenvironmental
48 conditions (Thulborn, 1991; Dentzien-Dias et al., 2012). Their exceptional preservation
49 of inclusions, preserving structures that would not have been preserved in the host rock,
50 qualifies them as *Konservat-Lagerstätten* (Seilacher et al., 2001; Qvarnström et al.,
51 2016; Dentzien-Dias et al., 2018). These inclusions may primarily consist of undigested
52 components, but they can also contain parasites from the intestinal tract or traces of
53 coprophagic organisms (Chin, 2007; Dentzien-Dias et al., 2013).

54 The fecal matter can preserve a wide variety of organisms, such as bacteria, fungi,
55 worms and protozoans, thus providing direct evidence of paleoecological interactions
56 (Qvarnström et al., 2016; Chin, 2021). This microenvironment record provides
57 information about the origin, evolution and temporal range of parasitic or symbiotic
58 lineages, their environmental distribution, coevolution with hosts, and ancient food web
59 dynamics (Dentzien-Dias et al., 2017; Qvarnström et al., 2016; De Baets et al., 2021;
60 De Baets et al., 2024). Despite recent studies on Permian coprolites and their
61 abundance, research on specimens from the Rio do Rasto Formation (Paraná Basin,
62 southern Brazil) remains limited.

63 This study aims to characterize the microbial, parasitic, and dietary inclusions
64 preserved within coprolites to reconstruct paleoecological interactions. Ninety-seven
65 coprolites from 11 outcrops of the Guadalupian-Lopingian (middle/upper Permian) Rio
66 do Rasto Formation were analyzed in search of paleoecological information. These
67 findings amplify the knowledge about the Permian vertebrates and their ecosystem in
68 the Rio do Rasto Formation.

69

70 **2. Geological setting**

71 The Paraná Basin is an extensive intracratonic basin (1.7 million km²) located in
72 southern Brazil, Argentina, Paraguay, and Uruguay. Its deposition occurred through
73 tectonic and eustatic cycles during the Paleozoic and Mesozoic in western Gondwana
74 (Holz et al., 2010). The Rio do Rasto Formation, representing the middle to upper
75 Permian (Roadian-Wuchiapingian) interval of the Paraná Basin, consists primarily of

76 deltaic, fluvial, and lacustrine deposits. This age determination is supported by U-Pb
77 zircon dating from tonstein bed (Francischini et al., 2018; Rocha-Campos et al., 2019).

78 The formation is subdivided into two members: the basal Serrinha Member,
79 representing a lacustrine system influenced by storm waves (Holz et al., 2010), and the
80 upper Morro Pelado Member, interpreted as deltaic deposits associated with lacustrine
81 and eolian dune environments (Kern et al., 2021; Schemiko, 2014).

82 The fossil record from the Rio do Rasto Formation is exceptionally rich, including
83 vertebrates (temnospondyls, sharks, actinopterygians, sarcopterygians and a diversity of
84 amniotes such as Archosauromorpha, Pareiasauria, Dinocephalia, and Anomodontia),
85 along with abundant plant fossils, invertebrates and ichnofossils (Rohn and Rösler,
86 1989; Ferreira-Oliveira and Rohn, 2010; Dentzien-Dias et al., 2012). In addition to this
87 wide variety, coprolites are particularly abundant in the formation (>1 000 collected
88 specimens; e.g., Dentzien-Dias et al., 2012, 2013, 2016; Rochinski and Dias, 2015;
89 Fontanelli and Vega, 2020). In spite of that, research on coprolites from this formation
90 remains limited.

91

92 **3. Material and Methods**

93 The study material was collected from 11 sites in southern Brazil, with 9 localities
94 in Rio Grande do Sul State and 2 in Paraná State (Fig. 1; Table 1). All the coprolites
95 were collected in pelitic levels, with associated fossils present in nearly all outcrops
96 examined (Table 1; Fig. 2). The material comprises 97 coprolites, examined using
97 various techniques: 94% through external observation, 5% with thin sections, and 1%
98 using computed tomography. The specimens are housed in three institutions: 66 at the
99 Museu de Paleontologia da UFRGS Irajá Damiani Pinto of the Universidade Federal do
100 Rio Grande do Sul (MPIDP-UFRGS), 28 at the Laboratório de Geologia e
101 Paleontologia of the Universidade Estadual do Oeste do Paraná (LGP-Unioeste), and 3
102 at the Museu de Ciências e Tecnologia of the Pontifícia Universidade Católica do Rio
103 Grande do Sul (MCT-PUCRS).

104 The coprolites were classified into three primary morphotypes: heteropolar
105 (exhibiting whorls in the posterior portion), amphipolar (with whorls along the entire
106 length), and non-spiral (no whorls along the entire length) (sensu Dentzien-Dias et al.,
107 2012). A fourth category, indeterminate spiral, was established for specimens with
108 whorls that could not be definitively classified as heteropolar or amphipolar.

109 Standardized color documentation was performed using the Munsell Soil Color
110 Chart. Morphometric measurements were obtained with vernier calipers, while surface
111 features and adhesion structures were examined under stereomicroscopy. For inclusions
112 analysis, petrographic thin sections were prepared from five coprolites (LGP-Csc-
113 1363.3C; LGP-Csc-1363.5C; LGP-Csc-1363.6B; LGP-Csc-1363.9C; LGP-Csc-
114 1363.11A) at the Laboratório de Geologia e Paleontologia (Unioeste) and Núcleo de
115 Preparação de Amostras (UFRGS), building upon previous work by Rochinski and Dias
116 (2015).

117 Eight specimens (UFRGS-PV-0361-P; UFRGS-PV-0365a-P; UFRGS-PV-0368-P;
118 UFRGS-PV-0532-P; UFRGS-PV-0736-P; UFRGS-PV-0743-P; UFRGS-PV-0749-P;
119 and UFRGS-PV-0753-P) underwent SEM analysis at the central portion. Samples were
120 mounted on Al stubs, coated with Au, and examined using a JEOL JSN-6610LV
121 Scanning Electron Microscope. Complementary mineralogical and chemical
122 characterization was achieved through Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) and
123 X-ray powder diffraction at the Laboratório de Difractometria de Raios X (Instituto de
124 Geociências, UFRGS).

125 Micro-CT scanning was performed on two coprolites from Santo Antônio Farm
126 (Table 1), at the Faculty of Computer Microtomography Laboratory, University of
127 Silesia, in Poland. Specimens UFRGS-PV-0535-P and UFRGS-PV-0374-P were
128 scanned using a GE v|tome|x s system with a DXR250 detector (2024 x 2024 pixels, 14-
129 bit depth, 0.2 mm pixel size) at 180 kV and 150 μ A with a 0.1 mm Cu filter. The setup
130 yielded a voxel size of 0.03300278 mm (33 μ m) for both X and Y axes, with 1300
131 projections over a 360° rotation. Data reconstruction used Phoenix datos|x 2 software,
132 with VGStudio MAX 2.1.1 as the primary analysis tool. Three-dimensional
133 reconstructions of coprolites and inclusions were generated using Avizo software,
134 enabling non-destructive visualization of internal structures.

135

136 **4. Results**

137 *4.1. External features*

138 The coprolites exhibit a range of colors, varying from reddish (10RP 4/10) to light
139 brown (10Y 8/2) and white (9.0/0), with some specimens covered by clayey
140 concretions. Two main morphotypes are present among the coprolites: spiral (63%) and
141 non-spiral (37%). The spiral morphotype was further divided into three subtypes:

142 heteropolar, amphipolar, or indeterminate spiral. Most coprolites belong to the spiral
143 morphotype (63%, N = 61), with the majority classified as the indeterminate spiral
144 subtype (37%, N = 37) (Fig. 3).

145 The heteropolar morphotype comprises 12% (N = 11) of the total sample (Fig. 3A;
146 Fig. 4A-B). The largest heteropolar coprolite (UFRGS-PV-0535-P) is 4.9 cm in length
147 and 2.5 cm in width, though its original size was likely larger due to fragmentation, as
148 well as all the other coprolites within this morphotype. Amphipolar coprolites represent
149 11% (N = 10) of the sample (Fig. 3B; Fig. 4C-D). The largest amphipolar coprolite
150 (UFRGS-PV-0374-P) measures 5.6 cm in length and 2 cm in width. In some cases,
151 excessive fragmentation and/or the presence of concretions prevented the identification
152 of the original morphology (heteropolar or amphipolar), despite the coprolites
153 displaying a spiral morphotype. These specimens were classified as indeterminate spiral
154 (Fig. 3C), representing 40% (N = 39) of the studied coprolites. The coprolites range
155 from 0.6 cm to 5.6 cm in length and 0.2 cm to 2.3 cm in maximum diameter, though
156 most are fragmented.

157 The non-spiral morphotype represents 37% (N = 37) of all coprolites (Fig. 3D).
158 Most non-spiral coprolites were collected from the Cândido de Abreu Outcrop, where
159 68% (N = 19) of the specimens were non-spiral. All specimens, except one (UFRGS-
160 PV-0741a-P), were fragmented, with measurements ranging from 0.5 cm to 8.7 cm in
161 length and 0.4 cm to 3.6 cm in maximum diameter. In four non-spiral coprolites
162 (UFRGS-PV-0733-P; MCP-3421-PV; MCP-3422-PV; and MCP-3423-PV), the only
163 preserved material is a thin layer adhered to the matrix rock, suggesting the coprolites
164 detached and only partial imprint remained (Fig. 5).

165

166 4.2. *Fish scales*

167 Fish scales constitute the majority of inclusions, occurring in almost all the
168 coprolites from all the morphotypes. The scales were observed using a
169 stereomicroscope, in petrographic thin sections, SEM analysis, and in micro-CT scans.
170 Coprolites with the highest abundance of fish scales are indeterminate spiral (mean:
171 22.6 scales per coprolite) and non-spiral (mean: 12.2 scales per coprolite). No
172 significant differences were detected between scales from different coprolites
173 morphotypes.

174 The scales occur on the external surface and within the interior of the coprolites.
175 Some are fragmented and typically not articulated, though they often appear in groups
176 aligned along the whorl border in spiral coprolites. While most scales are of similar
177 size, the presence of smaller specimens suggests variation in prey size. The majority
178 exhibit a ganoid structure, with distinct layers of bone, dentine, and ganoine (Fig. 6A).
179 A notable concentration of scales was also identified in two coprolites (UFRGS-PV-
180 0374-P and UFRGS-PV-0535-P), representing the amphipolar and heteropolar
181 morphotypes, using the micro-CT scan.

182

183 4.3. *Shark teeth*

184 Two shark teeth were identified in two distinct coprolites, non-spiral (UFRGS-PV-
185 0741a-P) and amphipolar (UFRGS-PV-0748-P), using a stereomicroscope (Fig. 6B).
186 The tooth from UFRGS-PV-0741a-P measures 1.69 mm in length, with only a portion
187 of the labial view visible (Fig. 6B). It preserves two cusps bearing longitudinal striae:
188 one central and a smaller one on the left side. The base is short, and a smooth apical
189 button is visible. These morphological characteristics closely resemble those of
190 Ctenacanthiformes Glikman, 1964.

191 The second tooth, from coprolite UFRGS-PV-0748-P, measures 1 cm in length, but
192 is fragmented in longitudinal section. Two lateral main cusps are visible, enabling
193 identification as Xenacanthiformes. The central cusp and base could not be
194 characterized due to fragmentation. Giving the absence of further diagnostic features, a
195 more specific taxonomic identification was not possible.

196

197 4.4. *Plants*

198 Plant remains and an insect wing impression were identified in the same non-spiral
199 coprolite (UFRGS-PV-0365b-P; beige color: 10Y 8/2) from the Minuano Farm site
200 (Fig. 6C, F). One impression measures 3.6 mm in length, exhibiting an elongated form
201 with parallel structures, likely representing a plant stem fragment. Although cellular
202 details are absent, the longitudinal striae strongly resemble those of Sphenophyte stems,
203 where the interfascicular area of the middle region of the internodes displays
204 rectangular, longitudinally aligned cells that appear striated (Rohn and Rösler, 1986).

205 Beneath this impression lies an epidermis fragment (1.62 mm) with longitudinally
206 aligned rectangular cell impressions (Fig. 6C). No additional diagnostic features are
207 preserved, precluding taxonomic identification.

208 SEM analysis revealed putative plant remains in two other Minuano Farm
209 coprolites (UFRGS-PV-0361-P; UFRGS-PV-0365a), including a longitudinally striated
210 fragment and a tracheid capillary (Fig. 6D-E). EDS analysis confirmed their organic
211 origin: the fragment in UFRGS-PV-0361-P showed peaks of calcium phosphate,
212 carbon, and oxygen, while UFRGS-PV-0365a exhibited these elements alongside
213 silicon, manganese, and iron.

214

215 4.5. *Insect wing*

216 Adjacent to the plant impressions in coprolite UFRGS-PV-0365b-P, an incomplete
217 insect wing impression was identified (Fig. 6F). The wing fragment measures 1.64 mm
218 in length, with only a small portion preserved. The impression exhibits a smooth
219 texture, distinct from the plant fragments, and displays two bifurcating veins. While
220 taxonomic attribution was not possible due to the fragmentary preservation and limited
221 diagnostic features, the wing's morphology shows strong similarities to *Petromantis*
222 *rieki* from the Permian of Brazil, particularly in the arrangement of the bifurcating veins
223 (Lara et al., 2023).

224

225 4.6. *Fungi*

226 Fungal remains, including hyphae and spores, were identified in all thin sections of
227 indeterminate spiral coprolites (LGP-Csc-1363.3C; LGP-Csc-1363.5C; LGP-Csc-
228 1363.6B; LGP-Csc-1363.9C; LGP-Csc-1363.11A) (Fig. 7, 8). Coprolites LGP-Csc-
229 1363.3C and LGP-Csc-1363.9C contain structures morphologically resembling the
230 modified hyphal wall of pseudoparenchymatous tissue characteristic of
231 Sordariomycetes peridium (Fig. 8A). Hyphae observed in LGP-Csc-1363.9C measure
232 approximately 53 μm in length. Fungal spores, occurring both in clusters and as isolated
233 specimens, were identified in LGP-Csc-1363.5C. These structures range from 6-22 μm
234 in length and 5-20 μm in width, with no associated asci or similar enclosing structures
235 (Fig. 8B). Based on morphological characteristics and dichotomous keys for dung-

236 inhabiting fungi (Bell, 1983; Doveri, 2004; van Asperen, 2021), the spores were
237 assigned to the genus *Sporormiella*.

238 The spores exhibit characteristic *Sporormiella* features, including cylindrical cells
239 with some displaying rounded ends. As with most fossil *Sporormiella* records, these
240 spores occur as individual cells rather than within the asci, as ascus walls are highly
241 ephemeral and rarely preserved fossilized feces.

242 Additional hyphae were observed via SEM in two other coprolites (UFRGS-PV-
243 0361-P; UFRGS-PV-0736-P) (Fig. 8C, D). In UFRGS-PV-0361-P, hyphae are
244 associated with yeast-like cells measuring 6-8 μm in diameter (Fig. 8C). EDS analysis
245 indicates these hyphal structures are composed primarily of carbon, silicon, and oxygen.
246

247 4.7. *Cyanobacteria*

248 The indeterminate spiral coprolite LGP-Csc-1363.5C contained both cylindrical
249 and coccoid cellular structures (Fig. 7; Fig. 9A, B). The cylindrical cells (7 μm
250 diameter) exhibit morphological similarity to Nostocales cyanobacteria (Komárek et al.,
251 2014), particularly in their linear organization. Seven such cells were preserved in the
252 specimen: five aligned linearly and two arranged parallel to this formation (Fig. 9A). No
253 heterocysts or cellular sheaths were observed in association with these structures.

254 Additionally, the coprolite contained numerous paired spherical cells (13-16.7 μm
255 diameter) classified as coccoid forms following traditional morphological criteria
256 (Komárek and Johansen, 2015) (Fig. 9B). These structures show morphological affinity
257 with extant Chroococcales (Komárek and Johansen, 2015). The substantial size of these
258 cells precludes identification as bacterial and supports their interpretation as
259 cyanobacterial remains.
260

261 4.8. *Non-filamentous Bacteria*

262 Rod-shaped bacilli measuring 4.4-5.6 μm in length were observed in thin sections
263 of the indeterminate spiral coprolite LGP-Csc-1363.5C (Fig. 7, 9C).

264 SEM analysis revealed rounded microbial colonies attached to the substrate in four
265 additional coprolite specimens (UFRGS-PV-0365a-P; UFRGS-PV-0532-P; UFRGS-
266 PV-0736-P; UFRGS-PV-0753-P), representing indeterminate spiral, amphipolar, and
267 non-spiral morphotypes. These colonies were covered by a film-like structure and

268 identified as Actinomycete colonies with associated biofilms based on characteristic
269 morphological features (Dentzien-Dias et al., 2017). The coccoid bacteria cells formed
270 cohesive colonies bound by extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) (Taylor et al.,
271 2009) (Fig. 9D-F).

272

273 4.9. *Cestoda* Eggs

274 An oval-shaped structure measuring 83 μm in length and 56 μm in width was
275 identified in the indeterminate spiral coprolite LGP-Csc-1363.3C (Fig. 7; Fig. 10A).
276 This structure exhibits morphological similarity to cestode eggs described by Dentzien-
277 Dias et al. (2013), displaying characteristic features including an ovoid shape, internal
278 filling, and an external capsule. Although isolated as a single egg without visible
279 embryophore, its identification as cestode is supported by diagnostic characteristics
280 (ovoid shape and smooth shell) matching previous descriptions (Dentzien-Dias et al.,
281 2013).

282 Three additional organic structures with cestode affinities were observed in LGP-
283 Csc-1363.5C (Fig. 10B). These differ from the previous specimen by their rounded
284 morphology (18 μm diameter) and radially striated shell (2.7 μm thickness). While no
285 internal embryo was preserved, the structures show striking resemblance to extant
286 *Taenia* eggs (Šlais, 1970), particularly in the presence of a thick, radially striated
287 embryophore. The significantly smaller size (approximately five-fold reduction)
288 precludes identification as pollen.

289

290 5. Discussion

291 The coprolites display a wide range of morphological variation. This variation can
292 result from several factors, including: the type of food ingested, the health condition of
293 the producer, or natural variations in the intestinal tract morphology of the producer
294 (Hunt et al., 1994). The valvular intestines that produce spiral feces represent a
295 plesiomorphic condition among vertebrates, having been secondarily lost only in
296 teleosts and tetrapods (Hunt et al., 1994; Hunt and Lucas, 2012). Since teleosts appear
297 to have originated in the Anisian (Middle Triassic; e.g., Arratia and Schultze, 2024), all
298 non-spiral coprolites described in this study are attributed to tetrapod producers. The
299 occurrence of two distinct spiral morphologies (heteropolar and amphipolar) results

300 from differences in intestinal valve anatomy. These morphotypes are attributed to non-
301 teleostean fishes possessing spiral valves, including elasmobranchs, paleonisciformes,
302 and sarcopterygians (Parker, 1879; McAlliester, 1985; Qvarnström et al., 2019).

303 The shark teeth were identified as belonging to Xenacanthiformes or showing
304 similarities to Ctenacanthiformes. Xenacanthiformes are well-documented in the Rio do
305 Rasto Formation, including species such as *Xenacanthus ragonhai*, *Xenacanthus*
306 *santosi*, and *Triodus richterae*, as well as numerous indeterminate specimens (Würdig-
307 Maciel, 1975; Pauliv et al., 2014, 2016, 2017). Ctenacanthiform sharks, known from the
308 Late Devonian to the Early Triassic, possess teeth characterized by a prominent central
309 cusp and smaller lateral cusps, with a broad and relatively short base (Hodnett et al.,
310 2021). The presence of these teeth suggests that sharks were prey for the animals that
311 produced the coprolites.

312 The occurrence of plant remains in three coprolites from the Minuano Farm
313 indicates herbivorous or omnivorous feeding behavior. The Sphenophytes identified in
314 one coprolite are consistent with plant taxa previously reported from the Rio do Rasto
315 Formation (Rohn and Rösler, 1986). However, nearly all coprolites across morphotypes
316 contain abundant fish scales, teeth, and bone fragments, strongly supporting a
317 predominantly carnivorous/piscivorous diet for most producers.

318 Carnivorous diets enhance coprolite preservation due to the high phosphate content
319 derived from hydroxylapatite in ingested vertebrate remains (e.g., scales, bones, teeth).
320 This phosphate facilitates permineralization, often requiring little to no additional
321 mineral enrichment (Bradley, 1946; Chin et al., 2003; Northwood, 2005; Hollocher and
322 Hollocher, 2012; Chin, 2021). The resulting phosphatic composition promotes
323 exceptional preservation of delicate structures, including soft tissues and parasitic
324 remains (Qvarnström et al., 2016). Furthermore, bacterial and fungal activity may
325 further enhance permineralization (Hollocher et al., 2001; Luo et al., 2023)

326 Bacterial decomposition generates localized zones saturated with crystallized
327 calcium phosphate. During organic matter breakdown, bacteria modify the chemical
328 gradients of surrounding water, releasing ions that react with groundwater components
329 and promote mineral precipitation (Hollocher et al., 2001; Bajdek et al., 2016). Notably,
330 some of these bacteria likely represent remnants of the producer's intestinal
331 microbiome. Bacterial remains have been identified in at least five coprolites through
332 thin-section and SEM analyses (LGP-Csc-1363.5C; UFRGS-PV-0365a-P; UFRGS-PV-

333 0532-P; UFRGS-PV-0736-P; UFRGS-PV-0753-P), confirming their role in
334 preservation processes.

335 As for the fungal elements, they occur exclusively within the coprolite matrix,
336 absent from surface areas, suggesting they represent coprophilous fungi from the
337 producer intestinal tract. The presence of fungal spores aligns with the life cycle of
338 coprophilous fungi: spores dispersed in the environment are ingested by animals, pass
339 through the digestive system, and germinate upon excretion (Richardson, 2001; Calaça
340 and Santos, 2017).

341 Recent studies demonstrate the significant diversity of dung-inhabiting fungal
342 spores preserved in coprolites, highlighting their value as non-pollen palynomorphs for
343 investigating past animal biodiversity and fungal evolution (van Asperen et al., 2016,
344 2021; Davies, 2019). Among these, *Sporormiella* spores represent one of the most
345 widely recognized and utilized indicators for studying megaherbivore population
346 dynamics and paleoecological reconstructions (van Asperen et al., 2021). This genus
347 commonly occurs in modern herbivore and omnivore dung and has also been
348 documented on decaying wood (Ahmed and Cain, 1972). *Sporormiella* exhibits a global
349 distribution across sub-boreal and temperate regions (Davis and Shafer, 2006) and
350 appears throughout the fossil record, typically as dispersed individual spores (Davis,
351 1987; Davis and Shafer, 2006). These spores spread passively and germinate in feces
352 following ingestion (Davis and Shafer, 2006).

353 In the current study, the carnivorous nature of the coprolite producer suggests the
354 fungal spores were likely ingested accidentally through waterborne transmission. The
355 fossil origin of these fungal remains is confirmed by EDS analysis revealing silicon
356 content. The remarkable morphological stasis observed in many fungal lineages enables
357 their identification in ancient coprolites.

358 A similar pattern occurs with cyanobacteria. These organisms exhibit extraordinary
359 evolutionary longevity with minimal morphological change. The Nostocales and
360 Chroococcales cyanobacteria identified in these coprolites have existed since the
361 Proterozoic (Taylor et al., 2009) and were presumably ingested from the aquatic
362 environment inhabited by the producer animals.

363 The presence of at least two distinct cestode egg morphotypes provides direct
364 evidence of parasitism. The eggs described by Dentzien-Dias et al. (2013) (145-155 μm
365 long x 88-100 μm wide) differ from those in our study by their larger size and grouped
366 arrangement within coprolite whorls (resembling proglottids). Those specimens showed

367 an embryophore containing putative somatic cells, with their cestode affinity confirmed
368 by egg morphology, operculum presence, and the proglottid-like deposition (Dentzien-
369 Dias et al., 2013). While our specimen is smaller, this may reflect sectional orientation
370 rather than true size disparity, as even the Coproland eggs exhibit dimensional variation.
371 The preservation of parasite body fossils is a rare event due to their microscopic size,
372 soft body, and intrahost location (De Baets et al., 2015). These factors further obscure
373 taxonomically diagnostic features, as seen in our material.

374 The three eggs from LGP-Csc-1363.5C display distinct characteristics (rounded
375 shape and radially striated shell) differing from Coproland specimens. Their
376 morphology closely resembles extant *Taenia* eggs, cestodes known to parasitize sharks
377 (Linton, 1924; Jensen, 2005). While Zangerl and Case (1976) reported similarly striated
378 eggs in a *Cobelodus aculeatus* cololite, their ovoid shape contrasts with our spherical
379 specimens, supporting our cestode classification.

380 The fossil record documents tapeworm (Cestoda) eggs from the Carboniferous
381 through the Holocene (De Baets et al., 2015, 2021). The earliest known cestode eggs
382 occur in a cololite preserved with its producer (*Cobelodus aculeatus*) from the
383 Pennsylvanian black shales of North America (Zangerl and Case, 1976). Permian
384 occurrences include cestode eggs in fish coprolites in Coproland, from the same
385 formation as our study material (Dentzien-Dias et al., 2013). Our findings of isolated
386 tapeworm eggs are of great interest as Paleozoic records previously contained only
387 grouped eggs, which may improve their preservation potential (De Baets et al., 2024).
388 In contrast, ascaridoid nematode eggs have been reported more commonly in Mesozoic
389 archosaur, fish and synapsid coprolites, and remain undocumented in Paleozoic
390 coprolites despite their generally high preservation potential.

391 The parasitic record in coprolites spans diverse taxa from the Permian to the
392 Holocene (De Baets et al., 2021; Chin, 2021), including protozoans (Ferreira et al.,
393 1992; Wood et al., 2013), nematodes (Bouchet et al., 2003; Barrios-de Pedro et al.,
394 2020), trematodes (Jouy-Avantin et al., 1999; Poinar and Boucot, 2006) and
395 acanthocephalans (Fry and Hall, 1969; Cardia et al., 2019). However, cestodes currently
396 represent the only parasites documented in fishes from the Rio do Rasto Formation. The
397 occurrence of a new cestode egg morphotype expands these parasites as the most
398 common group in the Permian. Further analyses should try to understand the reasons
399 (preservation or others) behind the dominance of eggs attributable to cestodes as
400 opposed to different kinds of intestinal parasites.

401 Previous studies have documented coprolites from the Rio do Rasto Formation at
402 various outcrops. Dentzien-Dias et al. (2012) described more than 500 specimens from
403 a single layer at Coproland (Rio Grande do Sul State), classifying heteropolar
404 morphologies into two subtypes: classic heteropolar and heteropolar edge. They also
405 identified a distinctive “knot” morphotype characterized by interlaced whorls layers
406 resembling a knot. Our study did not recover these specific morphotypes (heteropolar
407 edge or knot), potentially due to preservation biases as many of our specimens were
408 fragmented and classified as indeterminate spiral. Both studies recorded amphipolar
409 coprolites in relatively low numbers. The Coproland specimens contained abundant fish
410 scales, shell fragments, invertebrate burrows, and cestode eggs (Dentzien-Dias et al.,
411 2013).

412 Fontanelli and Vega (2020) reported coprolites from São Jerônimo da Serra
413 Outcrop (Paraná State) showing similar morphotype proportions to our material, with
414 non-spiral forms predominating. Most spiral specimens could not be classified as
415 heteropolar or amphipolar due to concretion cover. Nonetheless, these coprolites are
416 distinguished by their manganese-rich composition, which gives a characteristic dark
417 coloration contrasting with the beig-to-red coloration observed at other outcrops.
418 Inclusions primarily consist of fish scales (up to 70 per coprolite; mean: 16), with some
419 specimens containing bone fragments.

420

421 **6. Conclusions**

422 This study provides new insights into the coprolites of the Rio do Rasto Formation,
423 substantially expanding knowledge of this previously understudied aspect of the Rio do
424 Rasto Formation fossil record. Through detailed analysis of inclusions and preservation
425 features, we have identified probable producers, reconstructed dietary patterns, and
426 elucidated paleoecological relationships preserved within these trace fossils.
427 Furthermore, our findings reveal important details about the microenvironment
428 fossilized within the fecal matrix. Collectively, these results offer valuable contributions
429 to understanding Permian trophic dynamics and ecosystem interactions, establishing a
430 foundation for future research on coprolite paleobiology in the region.

431

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433

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731 **Figure captions**

732

733 **Figure 1.** Map indicating the sites where the coprolites were collected. **A**, Simplified
734 map of the states of Paraná, Santa Catarina and Rio Grande do Sul (Southern Brazil),
735 with the area where the Rio do Rasto Formation crops out (Modified from Dias and
736 Richter, 2002). Red dots indicate the outcrops in Paraná and Rio Grande do Sul; **B**,
737 Detailed map indicating the fossil sites in the state of Rio Grande do Sul.

738

739 **Figure 2.** Stratigraphic logs of the coprolite-bearing sites. **A**, Cândido de Abreu site
740 (Modified from Ferreira-Oliveira and Rohn, 2010); **B**, Invernada Farm site; **C**, Minuano
741 Farm site; **D**, Santo Antônio Farm site (Modified from Cisneros et al., 2021).

742

743 **Figure 3.** Coprolites morphotypes (A-D) and their proportion (E). **A**, Heteropolar
744 (UFRGS-PV-0535-P); **B**, Amphipolar (UFRGS-PV-0374-P); **C**, Indeterminate spiral
745 (UFRGS-PV-0750a-P); **D**, Non-spiral (UFRGS-PV-0741c-P); **E**, Graphic showing the
746 proportion of morphotypes found in the studied sites. Scale bars: A-C = 5 mm; D = 1
747 mm.

748

749 **Figure 4.** Micro CT scan of selected coprolites. **A**, Heteropolar coprolite (UFRGS-PV-
750 0535-P); **B**, Cross-section of coprolite UFRGS-PV-0535-P; **C**, Amphipolar coprolite
751 (UFRGS-PV-0374-P); **D**, Cross-section of coprolite (UFRGS-PV-0374-P). Scale bars:
752 A-D = 1 cm.

753

754 **Figure 5.** Non-spiral coprolites from Santo Antônio da Platina site. **A**, MCP-3422-PV;
755 **B**, MCP-3423-PV; **C**, MCP-3421-PV.

756

757 **Figure 6.** Inclusions found in the coprolites. **A**, Ganoid scales (LGP-Csc-1363.9C); **B**,
758 Tooth similar to Ctenacanthiformes (UFRGS-PV-0741a-P); **C**, Plant impressions
759 (UFRGS-PV-0365b-P). Arrows point where the impressions are located; **D**, Plant
760 fragment (UFRGS-PV-0361-P); **E**, Fragment of tracheid capillary (UFRGS-PV-0365a);
761 **F**, Insect wing impression (UFRGS-PV-0365b-P). Scale bars: A = 100 μm ; B = 0.5 mm;
762 C = 1 mm; D = 20 μm ; E = 2 μm ; F = 1 mm.

763

764 **Figure 7.** Non-alimentary inclusions found in the coprolites.

765

766 **Figure 8.** Fungal inclusions. **A**, Hyphal wall of a pseudoparenchymatous tissue (LGP-
767 Csc-1363.3C); **B**, Fungal spores (LGP-Csc-1363.5C); **C**, Hyphae associated with yeast-
768 like cells (UFRGS-PV-361-P); **D**, Fungal hyphae (UFRGS-PV-0361-P). Scale bars: A-
769 B = 10 μm ; C = 50 μm ; D = 20 μm .

770

771 **Figure 9.** Non-food inclusions. **A**, Cylindrical cells of cyanobacteria (LGP-Csc-
772 1363.5C); **B**, Coccoid cells of cyanobacteria (LGP-Csc-1363.5C); **C**, Bacilli bacteria
773 (LGP-Csc-1363.5C); **D**, Actinomycete (UFRGS-PV-0753-P); **E-F**, Actinomycete
774 colonies and biofilm (UFRGS-PV-0753-P). Scale bars: A = 10 μm ; B = 75 μm ; C = 10
775 μm ; D = 1 μm ; E = 5 μm ; F = 10 μm .

776

777 **Figure 10.** Cestode eggs. **A**, LGP-Csc-1363.3C; **B**, LGP-Csc-1363.5C. Scale bars: A =
778 25 μm ; B = 10 μm .

□ Rio do Rasto Formation

● Site

● City

— Main roads

1- Santo Antônio da Platina Outcrop

2- Cândido de Abreu Outcrop

3- Boqueirão Farm

4- Pt 20 Outcrop

5- Nossa Senhora do Horto Farm

6- Minuano Farm

7- Santo Antônio Farm

8- São Jorge Farm

9- Jagunço Farm

10- Invernada Farm

11- Nossa Senhora de Lourdes Farm

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■ Heteropolar ■ Amphipolar ■ Indeterminate spiral ■ Non-spiral

Site	Locality	Geology	Fossil record	Reference
Cândido de Abreu	Cândido de Abreu, Paraná (PR-487) S24°39.020' W51°13.773'	Thick succession of meter scale red mudstones and fine sandstones including at least four eolian dune beds	Leaiid conchostracans, plants, fish scales, Temnospondyli amphibians, invertebrate ichnofossil, coprolites	Ferreira-Oliveira and Rohn, 2010
Santo Antônio da Platina	Santo Antônio da Platina, Paraná (BR 153)	Carbonaceous siltite; yellowish sediment	Conchostraca, Paleonisciformes, coprolites	Dias, 2012
Boqueirão Farm	São Gabriel, Rio Grande do Sul S30°00'04" W54°05'06"	Pelites intercalated with clay lenses, sand and intraformational conglomerates	<i>Pampaphoneus biccai</i> (Dinocephalia), <i>Rastodon procurvidense</i> (Dicynodontia), <i>Konzhukovia sangabrielensi</i> (Temnospondyli), coprolites	Cisneros et al., 2012; Boos et al., 2016; Pacheco et al., 2017
Pt 20	São Gabriel, Rio Grande do Sul	Pelitic level	Coprolites	Present work
Jagunço Farm	São Gabriel, Rio Grande do Sul	Pelitic level	Coprolites	Present work
Nossa Senhora do Horto Farm	Hulha Negra, Rio Grande do Sul S30°50'1.19" W54°57'6.79"	Pelites intercalated with sandstones and ripple marks	Fragmented bones, petrified wood, coprolites	Present work
Invernada Farm	Hulha Negra, Rio Grande do Sul S31°46'19.59" W53°54'12.98"	Massive siltite intercalated with fine sandstone and conglomerates, with a paleosol level	Dipnoi, Xenacanthiform teeth, indeterminate tetrapod, coprolites	Present work
Nossa Senhora de Lourdes Farm	Hulha Negra, Rio Grande do Sul S31°58'0.21" W53°53'12.40"	Pelite with conglomerates lenses	Petrified wood, coprolites	Present work
Minuano Farm	Aceguá, Rio Grande do Sul	Siltite with plane-parallel lamination intercalated with clay and sandstones lenses; grayish sediment	Petrified wood, invertebrate ichnofossil, coprolites	Present work
Santo Antônio Farm	Aceguá, Rio Grande do Sul S31°49'50.38" W54° 5'43.76"	Sequence of massive/poorly laminated siltstone intercalated by small conglomerate levels and massive sandstone	<i>Provelosaurus americanus</i> (Pareiasauridae) remains, fish teeth and scales, plant impressions (<i>Glossopteris communis</i> , sphenophytes), petrified wood, coprolites	Cisneros et al., 2021
São Jorge Farm	Aceguá, Rio Grande do Sul	Pelitic level	Coprolites	Present work
Table 1. Information about the sites studied.				

	Present work	São Jerônimo da Serra Outcrop	Coproland
Heteropolar	12%	14%	74%
Amphipolar	10%	4%	14%
Indeterminate spiral	40%	27%	
Non-spiral	38%	55%	12%
Inclusions	Fish scales, bone fragments, shark teeth, plants, insect wing, fungi, cyanobacteria, bacteria, cestode eggs	Fish scales and bone fragments	Fish scales, bone fragments, teeth, shell fragments, cestode eggs

Table 2. Comparison between the coprolites studied in this work and the coprolites collected in São Jerônimo da Serra Outcrop and Coproland.